

STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS CORE BANKING INCONVENIENCE & REMEDIES: A CASE STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO RURAL STUDENTS OF MANGALORE TALUK OF DAKSHINA KANNADA

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ABSTRACT:

Technological advancements in the country gave great push to the banking field and brought massive changes in the mode of banking operations. Installation of Core Banking Solutions paved the way for the introduction of various digital initiatives by the bankers, which are highly appreciated by younger generation customers, particularly by students. This paper attempts to highlight the digital inconvenience in rural parts of Mangalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, caused due to infrastructure deficit like lack of digital identity, lack of high speed network coverage, safe cyber etc. The study is based upon the opinions given by 100 rural undergraduate students of Mangalore taluk of Dakshina Kannada district, residing in Haleyangadi, Pavanje, Challairu, Thokur and Aikala region. Majority of students, particularly female students are relatively recent entrants to internet based services. The study is carried out by conducting a survey by using a structured questionnaire. Understanding the attitude of students towards digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions, their expectations from digital initiatives, and understanding the digital inconvenience faced by the students are the objectives of study,

Key words: Technology advancements, Core Banking Solutions, Digital initiatives, Digital inconvenience

INTRODUCTION:

One of the latest technological developments in the field of banking in recent times is the concept of digitalization. Paperless transactions through computers and mobile phones are most common among younger generation customers. In fact digitalization of transactions is made possible because of the compulsory installation of Core Banking Solutions by Bankers as per the directives issued by Reserve Bank of India. Digital India campaign launched by our honorable Prime minister Sri Narendra Modi on 1st July 2015 is a great step considering the need for economic development and prosperity of the country. But there are also a lot of problems and difficulties being faced by everyone at some or other points, needless to say, including in Digital banking field. Lack of knowledge about the latest development in the field of technology, fear about the security of

transactions and poor internet connectivity are the major drawbacks for digitalization of banking transactions in some of the rural areas of the country, including in Dakshina Kannada district.

OBJECTIVES:

- a) To know the perceptions of rural students of Managalore taluk towards digital banking
- b) To understand the expectations of the respondents towards digital banking
- c) To focus on inconveniences faced by rural students of Managalore taluk in using various digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY:

Digital inconvenience is the major issue tickling the minds of bankers in the process of implementation of digital banking strategies including CBS. Installation of Core Banking Software involves huge investment, and it requires 100% information technology support. India, being a country with mass rural population, striving very hard to make this digital India campaign very popular in every field including the banking field. Moreover, this topic is of utmost relevance considering efforts put up by bankers to improvise and satisfy the requirements of varied types of customers. Hence this study is undertaken to understand the problems faced by rural students of Managalore taluk in using various digital initiatives of Core Banking Solutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Chirag Patel, Darshan Ranpura etl.(2013) in their research article “Rural Banking Through Internet: A Study on Use of Internet Banking Among Rural Consumers” opined that role of rural banks in Indian financial sector is important, but not pre eminent. Rural banking is more inclusive of low income group families whose usage level of technological devices like smart phones and computers is lower. In the recent past, since one year they have been using internet banking mainly for balance enquiry and their usage of internet banking for other purposes is very limited.

Sahadeb Sukla Dasa(2016) in his research paper “ Study of digital banking facilities: with reference to Guwahati in Kamrup (metro) district of Assam” threw light on various digital banking services provided by banks to customers in Assam. He found from his study that Network failure, Error in operation, No security for internet dealing, No Authenticated records, Low Speed and Delay are the main problems faced by the bankers in digital banking.

Ameena Farooqui and P.Rajani (2017) in their research article “**E-Banking Issues & Challenges**” analysed the progress of internet banking in India. They have highlighted Security risk, lack of trust factor in internet banking, Lack of customer awareness, Fear of disclosing private information, failure to adopt global technology as the main challenges restricting the adoption of internet banking in India.

Raghavendra Nayak (2018) in his research article “A Conceptual study on digitalization of banking-issues and challenges” opined that digitalisation of banking transactions is concerned with providing efficient services to customers along with a large opportunity to gain in the years to come. Higher capital formation in the banking sector is the outcome of digitalisation of banking. But digital move in rural parts of the country is not that encouraging as, many problems and challenges have to be addressed in rural parts of the economy while introducing concept of digital banking. According

to him, providing digital infrastructure to rural parts of the country, creating awareness among rural customers about digital initiatives are major challenges on the part of bankers.

Several researchers have studied the advantages and challenges of Digital banking which is the outcome of Core Banking Solutions installed by the bankers. But hitherto no study is made about Students' perception towards Core Banking inconvenience& remedies in Mangalore Taluk. Hence to fill this research gap, this study is undertaken.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study is empirical and analytical in nature. Both Primary and Secondary data are used for the purpose of study. Primary data is collected by conducting a survey among 100 students of rural parts of Mangalore Taluk residing in Haleyangadi, Pavanje, Challairu, Thokur and Aikala region. Secondary data is incorporated from Journals, newspapers and internet. Descriptive statistics Mean, Standard Deviation and Percentage Mean are the Statistical tools used for the Analysis and interpretation of data.

HYPOTHESES:

I. Core Banking Channels and willingness of rural students to use them for their banking operations

H0: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are not willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

H1: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

II. Perceptions of respondents about Core banking inconveniences in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H0: Respondents perceive that, there are no inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk.

H1: Respondents perceive that, there ar inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

DATA ANALYSIS:

Table 1: Demographic profile of Respondents

Demographic factors	Classification	Number of Respondents	Percent
Gender	Male	45	45
	Female	55	55
	18-20 years	35	35

Age group	20-22 years	38	38
	22 to 24 years	23	23
	24 to 26 years	04	04
Monthly Family income	Less than Rs.20,000	15	15
	Rs. 20,000 to Rs.30,000	20	30
	Rs.30,000 to Rs.40,000	33	33
	Rs.40,000 to Rs.50,000	22	22
	Rs.50,000 and above	10	10
Educational course Opted for study	PUC	04	04
	Graduation	47	47
	Post Graduation	15	15
	Professional Course	24	24
	Diploma course	10	10

Source: Primary data

From Table 1, it is clear that both male and female students of different age group belonging to different family income groups, pursuing different educational courses are surveyed for collecting their opinions regarding Core Banking Solutions and their inconvenience& remedies.

Table 2: Distribution of students on the basis of their perception regarding Core Banking Solutions

Core Banking Channels help in different ways and Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean/SD	%Mean
	00 (0%)	02 (2%)	00 (0%)	54 (54%)	44 (44%)	3.42±0.5379	81.5%

Source: primary data

Testing of Hypothesis:

III. Core Banking Channels and willingness of rural students to use them for their banking operations

H0: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are not willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

H1: Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations

Table 2 clearly shows that none of the respondents (zero percent) strongly disagree, 2 percent of respondents disagree, zero percent of respondents neither agree nor disagree, while 54 percent of the respondents agree and 44 percent of respondents strongly agree that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations.

The percentage mean shows that 81.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.42 ± 0.5379) respondents strongly opine that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations as it falls in the category of 81% to 100%.

Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is justified. We therefore conclude that Rural students of Managalore Taluk of Dakshina Kannada are willing to use Core banking channels for their banking operations.

Table 3: Perceptions of respondents about CORE BANKING Inconveniences

Sl No	Problems	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean/ SD	% Mean
1	Digital illiteracy is the problem for the success of Core Banking system in rural areas of Mangalore taluk	00 (0%)	38 (38%)	00 (00%)	50 (50%)	12 (12%)	2.74±0.664	68.5%
2	Inadequate Digital net work is a problem for Core banking in rural areas	00 (0%)	00 (0%)	28 (28%)	38 (38%)	34 (34%)	4.0600 ±.79308	81.2%
3	Rural	00	00	00	50	50	3.5±0.505	

	customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud	(0%)	(0%)	(0%)	(50%)	(50%)		87.5%
4	Digital connectivity is not good in rural areas	08 (8%)	32 (32%)	00 (0%)	42 (42%)	18 (18%)	2.70±0.864	67.5%
5	Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas	00 (0%)	24 (24%)	00 (00%)	46 (46%)	30 (30%)	3.06±0.739	76.5%

Source: primary data

Testing of Hypothesis:

IV. Perceptions of respondents about Core banking inconveniences in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H0: Respondents perceive that, there are no inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

H1: Respondents perceive that, there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk

Table 3 shows Mean, Standard deviation and Percentage mean calculated on the perceptions of respondents about the inconvenience in the usage of Core banking channels .Percentage mean on each factor falls in the category of 61% to 100% which clearly shows that respondents agree that there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS in rural areas. Mean and Standard deviation presented in table 3 on various factors also justify the same.

Hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is justified. We therefore conclude that there are inconveniences in the usage of CBS Channels in rural parts of Managalore Taluk.

FINDINGS:

- 54 percent of the respondents agree and 44 percent of respondents strongly agree that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations.

- The percentage mean shows that 81.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.42 ± 0.5379) respondents strongly opine that Core banking channels have been useful in different ways and rural students of Mangalore Taluk are willing to use them for their banking operations
- Digital illiteracy is the problem for the success of Core Banking system in rural areas of Managalore taluk. Percentage mean shows that 68.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 2.74 ± 0.664) respondents agree that Digital illiteracy is hindrance for the usage of Core Banking channels in rural parts of Mangalore Taluk.
- Inadequate Digital net work is a problem for Core banking in rural areas. Percentage mean shows that 81.2% (Mean and Standard Deviation $4.0600 \pm .79308$) respondents strongly agree that Digital network is inadequate in rural areas.
- Rural customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud. Percentage mean reveals that 87.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 3.5 ± 0.505) respondents strongly agree that rural customers have greater fear about safety and security of transactions and about internet fraud.
- Digital connectivity is not good in rural areas. Percentage mean discloses that 67.5% (Mean and Standard Deviation 2.70 ± 0.864) respondents agree that digital connectivity is not good in rural areas.
- Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas. Statistical tools obtained for the data collected from the respondents are Percentage mean 76.5%, Mean and Standard deviation 3.06 ± 0.739 . Results clearly indicate that in the opinion of respondents, Network failure, low speed and delay in conducting the transactions are the major problems in rural areas .

REMEDIES AND SUGGESTIONS FOR CBS INCONVENIENCES IN RURAL AREAS:

- Creation of better digital infrastructure is necessary
- Digital education will help to create better awareness among customers
- Creation of digital information cell would help a lot in fulfilling the needs of rural customers
- Creation of Broadband connectivity for all citizens is necessary
- Greater safety must be ensured to customers to preserve the privacy of their transactions

CONCLUSION

Core banking channels play a very important role in digitalizing banking transactions across the country. It is true that there are some rural areas in India, which are lagging behind in infrastructural development. A large number of customers belong to economically weaker sections and they lack computer literacy and are hesitant to use technological devices for their banking transactions. There is a need to create more awareness among customers, particularly among customers of middle age about the latest developments in technology in rural areas. Committee could be set up by the government from Panchayath level in this regard.. Digital education in High Schools should be made compulsory so as to teach students as to how to work with online banking service and how technical issues relating to Core Banking channels can be addressed. Technology when used wisely will definitely produce good results. Core Banking Solutions is not an exemption; CBS software has already marked its own place in the Banking field by making 24X 7days banking possible around the globe.

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